

Application jarwo super technology as adaptive environmental friendly for rice in Jambi tidal swamp areas

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ABSTRACT

Agricultural technology to improve the optimization of swamp land areas was already existed, but rice productivity is still low. The latest technology that was already proven to increase irrigated rice productivity called Jarwo Super which will be verified in tidal swamp land areas. The purpose of this study was to obtain the influence of Jarwo super technology components on increasing rice production from 3.5 t/ha to 5 t/ha in tidal swamp areas. The research was carried out on the farmer's land area of three hectare in Karya Baru Village, Rantau Rasau District, East Tanjung Jabung Regency, Jambi Province. Assembled Jarwo Super technology was applied on land owned by three cooperative farmers using two new superior varieties namely Inpara 2 and Inpara 8 and Biotara fertilization. The results of the study showed that Jarwo super technology application with VUB Inpara 2 provided dry production yields of 6 t/ha equivalent to 5.1 t/ha dry rice. The yield of rice obtained by this Jarwo super technology application is 71.43% higher than the average productivity obtained by farmers' practices in wet season planting time. Jarwo Super technology can technically be carried out on tidal swamp land and was socially very acceptable to farmers (Stakeholders) because it can harvest in dry season planting time of 2017, where farmers usually fail to harvest the rice. Economically, Jarwo Super technology package in tidal swamp land gives benefits to farmers, this is indicated by the value of $R/C > 1$. Farming income analyses of Inpara 2 variety was Rp. 30,000,000 and Rp. 22,600,000 for Inpara 8 varieties by applying this technology.

Keywords: Jarwo super, inpara 2, inpara 8, tidal swamp areas, Jambi

INTRODUCTION

Currently, Indonesian government through Ministry of Agriculture is intensively developing tidal swamp land as a source of production food areas for people feed (Alihamsyah, 2002; Dirjen Tanaman Pangan 2009). It has been more than 30 years of research and study agricultural development and innovation technology in tidal land, but rice productivity is still low (Ar-Riza, 2002; Alihamsyah, 2003; Notohadiprawiro, 2006). Accordingly, it requires a new breakthrough to overcome this dilemma. One effort that can be done is by

applying Jarwo Super (JS) technology in tidal land. Previously, Jarwo Super technology had been studied and applied in irrigated rice fields which provided satisfactory rice production (Jamil et al, 2016).

Tidal swamp land area is one type of marginal land that has the potential to be developed as a new land expansion and areas for crop cultivation, especially rice (Tanaka, 1976; Widjaja-Adhi and Alihamsyah, 1998). Tidal swamp land in Jambi Province covering 39,538 ha (BPS, 2015). One of the tidal rice production centers in Jambi Province is located in East Tanjung Jabung Regency with a land area covered about 18,322 ha in 2015. However, the rice productivity of tidal swamp land in Jambi Province is still low, ranging from 3.00 to 3.90 t/ha (Jumakir, 2014). The purpose of this paper is to determine the effect of Jarwo Super technology on increasing rice production in tidal swamp land in Jambi.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The research for constructing JS technology in tidal swamp area was carried out from March to November 2017. The research was utilized demonstration farm spaces of JS technology in tidal swamp land area of east Tanjung Jabung Regency by involving three farmers as research cooperators. Around 3 hectares of more than 50 hectares rice area was used as demonstration plot. Research also exercised the latest swamp rice varieties assembled by Indonesian Swamp Land Research Institute and Indonesian Rice Research Center, with the intention of finding newly rice variety that has the potential highest production and will be adapted completely by farmers. In addition, water management technology and the use of Biotara biofertilizers, both will be studied to get the best technology combination. The JS technological innovation package will be compared with farmers cultivation technology in Jambi tidal swamp areas specific location. Materials and supporting tools for rice cultivation are used in accordance with agricultural technologies recommendations.

Rice cultivation in tidal swamp land area, using on Farm adaptive research (OFR) method, which was a large-scale assessment on farmers' land areas. The agricultural technology components both assembled and applied, were JP technologies and water management technology. The experiment was arranged on a split plot design with two factors, repeated three times. The first factor as the main plot was the application of biological fertilizers (Biotara) or control (without biological fertilizer) and the second factor or sub-plot was variety. The details of treatment are: Biotara (B) and variety (V) using: One-way water system only; with both Biotara (B) as B1 = Giving Biotara and B0 = without giving Biotara; and Varieties (V), V1 = Inpara 2 and V2 = Inpara 8.

Data to be collected during activities include economic data, agronomic data and farming system application base on economic and social data feasibility as supporting activities of farming system-image descriptions

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The JS application was carried out in dry season planting time 2017 with application of water management technology, Biotara biological fertilizer and newly adaptive rice varieties in tidal swamp land areas have been able to increase rice productivity (Saraswati, 2012). The effect of Biotara fertilizer application using both newly rice varieties of Inpara 2 and Inpara 8 varieties can be seen in agronomic parameters and yield components (Figure 1.).

Plant height, number of tillers, yield and yield components can be used as a benchmark to determine the effect of Biotara fertilizer on Inpara 2 and 8 varieties on the growth and yield of rice in tidal swamp land. Observations show that Biotara as biological fertilizer application can increase plant height, yield and yield components (Adesemoye and Kloepper. 2009).

A technology is suitable for implementation by farmers if the technology meets the requirements of technical, economic and social aspects (Yoshida, 1981; Wihardjaka et al, 1998; Mukhlis, 2009). Technically, JS technology in tidal swamp land areas can be applied by farmers because some technological components package was studied previously by farmers such as: cultivated *jajarlegowo* planting system (2: 1 and 4: 1), young seedling age, essentially used 2-3 seedling per hole, rice transplanter-machinery application, Integrated Pest Management (IPM) for controlling disease/pests,

In general, rice technology components and cultivated technical activities in tidal swamp land were already known by farmers with additional used of agricultural machinery such as three-wheeled mini-tractors to cultivate land, the use of Jarwo Transplanter as a mechanical planting tool was already be done in this research area with cooperator farmers as users. Local government for Food Crops, Horticulture and Plantation institution in East Tanjung Jabung district has provided assistance to a number of agricultural machinery to farmer groups. There is also a combine harvester that can be used during rice harvesting time.

Figure 1. Rice height, yield and yield components of JS Technology in tidal swamp areas Jambi

Biotara application in Inpara 2 shown a significantly different in parameters such as tiller length, empty grain, weight of 1000 grain and yields. Whereas, for rice height there was no significant different for all applications. Generally, application of Biotara gave a better rice production for both Inpara 2 and 8 varieties.

Economically, JS technology package in tidal swamp land gives benefits to farmers, this was indicated by the value of $R/C > 1$ (Table 1), meaning that the output obtained by farmers were greater than input (Soekartawi, et al. 1986).

Table 1. Farming Systems Analysis for JS Technology in Tidal Swamp Areas.

Components	Treatments			
	B0V1	B0V2	B1V1	B1V2
InputCost (Rp)	4.051.000	4.051.000	4.301.000	4.301.000
Labour	8.640.000	8.640.000	8.800.000	8.800.000
Production Income (Rp)	19.200.000	17.600.000	30.000.000	22.800.000
R/C	1,51	1,39	2,29	1,74

Source: Primary Data Analyses

CONCLUSIONS

The yield of rice obtained by JS technology application was 71.43% higher than the average productivity obtained by farmers' practices in wet season planting time in Jambi. JS technology can technically be carried out on tidal swamp land and was socially very acceptable for farmers (stakeholders) because rice can be harvested in dry season planting time of 2017, where farmers usually fail to get the yield.

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